

Bridging Policy and Practice in EMI: Peer Learning as a Classroom Interaction Strategy

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Abstract: *English-Medium Instruction (EMI) lecture courses and programs have become common in higher education across non-English-speaking countries. EMI programs are often implemented to advance internationalization, improve English proficiency, and to increase access to global academic communities. However, many EMI classes remain lecture-centered with limited opportunities for student interaction, language practice, or collaborative content learning. This article argues that short, structured peer learning exchanges provide a practical, scalable way to address this gap without compromising content coverage. Drawing on sociocultural and interactionist perspectives, as well as experience in a Japanese university context, the article distinguishes peer learning from longer-term collaborative learning models and explains why peer learning is more compatible with EMI lectures that often have time, pacing, and proficiency constraints. By integrating frequent, low-stakes, linguistically scaffolded interaction points into lectures, instructors can support comprehension, reduce affective barriers, and promote greater participation. A peer learning approach has the potential to make EMI lectures more interactive, inclusive, and aligned with the broader goals of EMI.*

Keywords: English Medium Instruction (EMI), peer learning, teaching strategies, active learning, student engagement, higher education

Introduction

English-Medium Instruction (EMI) has become a common part of many higher education curricula in non-English speaking countries. Universities around the world offer specialized courses taught in English with some institutions offering entire English language degree programs. These initiatives are often part of efforts to increase internationalization, global competitiveness, and access to academic communities (Macaro, 2018). While the theory underpinning EMI typically cites the dual ambition of content understanding and English language development, the implementation of EMI in practice often focuses on the content goals while overlooking the structured interaction necessary for language development and deeper comprehension (Airey, 2020; Aizawa & Rose, 2019; Wilkinson, 2018). In many EMI classrooms, this results in a persistent gap between policy goals and classroom practice, particularly in student-to-student interaction, where limited opportunities

for interaction prevent students from using English to process content, negotiate meaning, and build disciplinary understanding. This paper responds to this gap by proposing short, scalable peer learning exchanges as an interactional model suitable for lecture-based EMI courses that face time, English language proficiency, and participation constraints.

One of the main issues across EMI higher education contexts is the mismatch between the policy and reasoning and actual classroom realities. Many EMI classrooms remain lecture-centered with limited student participation, low rates of student-initiated questions, and limited opportunities for dialogic knowledge building (Duran & Sert, 2021). For students trying to process specified content in a second or foreign language, this lack of interaction can increase their burden as they try to interpret the subject matter and unfamiliar academic English, often without meaningful opportunities to negotiate or verify comprehension (Macaro et al., 2018).

Studies from Japanese university EMI classrooms reveal similar patterns. Students report hesitancy to speak due to concerns about their English ability, and some students may feel hesitant to speak in front of classmates (Aizawa & Rose, 2019; Galloway et al., 2017). Given the limited interaction outlined in these studies, it is possible that many students' engagement remains receptive and individual rather than interactional and co-constructed with peers.

Despite calls for more active EMI pedagogy, some proposed solutions emphasize collaborative learning models that are typically more structured and continuous over longer periods. While valuable, these models can be difficult to integrate in content lecture courses that face significant time constraints, large class enrollments, and strict pacing to ensure the content goals are reached. Consequently, many EMI courses do not incorporate practical, classroom-ready approaches that are manageable for large class sizes and can be used consistently without compromising the content portion of the lecture.

This paper proposes peer learning in the form of short, structured learning exchanges where students learn through interaction as a practical way to address participation and comprehension barriers in EMI classes. This form of peer learning differs from collaborative learning in duration, structure, interdependence, and assessment expectations. It does not require long-term group commitments, collaborative creation of materials, or ongoing tasks requiring students to meet outside class. Instead, it centers on brief, repeatable verbal or written exchanges that periodically break up lectures and create recurring opportunities for students to process content and language together.

Peer Learning Theory and Pedagogy

With the prevalence of EMI and subsequent research interest in this approach to education, there has been a growing body of research examining how students learn in these environments. Peer learning is grounded in sociocultural theory, which posits that learning is mediated through social interaction and cognitive development is facilitated via dialogic co-construction of meaning (Vygotsky, 1978). In EMI contexts, where language mediates access to the content, interaction is not a supplementary activity but a central process for learning. Therefore, peer exchanges provide an accessible approach for supporting both comprehension and language development during lectures.

Complementary to sociocultural perspectives, interactionist theories highlight the importance of negotiation, output, and modified interaction for language-mediated learning (Long, 1996; Swain,

2006). Through peer exchange, students can clarify understanding, summarize and paraphrase the lecture content in their own words, share their ideas about the content and language, and jointly resolve any breakdowns in meaning. These brief interactional exchanges help students to test their interpretations, compare reasoning, and refine their understanding of the content. These actions can reinforce both content learning and academic English development.

Peer learning can address known affective barriers in EMI classrooms. Compared to teacher-centered interaction, peer exchange can reduce social evaluation pressure as the interaction occurs in pairs or small groups, increases willingness to communicate, and lowers linguistic anxiety. These factors are all key to increasing participation in EMI environments (Kao, 2024; Tenenbaum, et al., 2020). These short peer exchanges create time for students to practice engaging with the content and using the language in a low-stakes environment without the fear of making mistakes in front of the whole class. Because the exchanges require students to articulate, check, and adjust their understanding, they also promote deeper processing and more permanent learning.

Short peer learning exchanges can be an efficient approach for EMI lectures because they require minimal class time, preserving syllabus goals and content coverage. Unlike long-term collaborative projects, these exchanges do not rely on sustained group obligations and can be implemented without significant changes to curriculums, making them particularly suitable for large classes. These exchanges also provide immediate diagnostic feedback by highlighting gaps in content comprehension during lectures (Tullis & Goldstone, 2020) allowing students to ask clarifying questions when needed. Another important aspect is such exchanges allow for shared meaning building among the learners rather than maintaining a focus on the instructor. This redistribution of knowledge building increases engagement and co-construction of meaning which work to increase understanding (Zhang & Bayley, 2019; Noroozi & De Wever, 2023). Empirical evidence consistently shows that short peer discussions improve accuracy, confidence, and retention, supporting their integration as a scalable, evidence-based approach to EMI teaching (Tenenbaum, et al., 2020).

While some collaborative learning approaches emphasize long-term involvement that often leads to the production of student-generated materials (e.g., joint presentations or semester projects), short peer exchanges emphasize interactional frequency, reciprocity, and joint knowledge building. In EMI lectures where curricular pacing is not always flexible and cannot accommodate long collaborative projects, short peer learning exchanges offer a more realistic, sustainable interactional model.

EMI Classroom Interaction Constraints

Research on EMI consistently identifies limited classroom interaction as a structural and pedagogical concern. Some large-scale studies (Macaro et al., 2018; Galloway et al., 2017) confirm that EMI courses frequently adopt an instructor-centered style of instruction where students receive the content in a passive manner. Duran and Sert (2021) observed that student-initiated questions in EMI university lectures were rare, illustrating that the interactional relationship of many EMI classrooms is one-sided with the instructor primarily speaking and the students mainly listening. This type of interaction may limit opportunities for negotiating meaning and can reduce students' sense of agency in the learning process.

A related trend is that even when students comprehend lecture content, they may lack

opportunities to use language for content related reasoning, reducing both linguistic development and deeper content consolidation (Yu & Kaur, 2024). Rather than treating interaction as optional or supplementary, EMI research frameworks emphasize the need to carefully study how content delivery and interaction are balanced (Curle & Pun, 2024).

Japanese higher education mirrors global EMI interactional constraints but includes additional sociolinguistic and cultural layers. Students often avoid speaking in English due to self-perceived lack of proficiency, fear of making errors, and classroom norms that value attentive silence (Aizawa & Rose, 2020; Macaro, 2018). In some contexts, this silence may be interpreted as comprehension rather than misunderstanding or communicative disengagement. This misalignment between instructor perceptions and student needs can reinforce passive learning in EMI classes. These conditions underscore the need for an approach that increases interaction among students in EMI classes.

Galloway et al. (2017) observe that institutional EMI expansion in Japan has outpaced EMI-specific faculty training, leaving many instructors without concrete strategies for English-inclusive pedagogy. In EMI contexts where instructors do not provide targeted opportunities for students to engage with the content and keep the focus of the lectures on their delivery, students will feel hesitant to speak out and interaction will remain minimal. Such constraints underscore the need for an instructional approach that increases interaction without losing content coverage. Peer learning offers such a solution by providing brief, structured opportunities for meaning-making that can be easily implemented into lecture-based EMI courses considering their realities.

Why Interaction Matters in EMI

Interaction in EMI is not only a linguistic opportunity but a fundamental way that students can process and work through academic content (Mercer, 2019). Swain (2000) contends that when students express their reasoning to their peers through summarizing, questioning, or verifying their understanding, comprehension becomes easier to notice, open for students and instructors to negotiate, and open to be revised. Without structured interaction, EMI lectures are at risk of only achieving surface-level comprehension, which can include note-taking, memorization, and passive listening (Airey, 2012). When this occurs, EMI classes fail to support the deeper cognitive engagement necessary for content understanding (Storch, 2013).

Research has shown that students develop more in-depth conceptual knowledge when they verbalize, test, and revise their interpretations through interaction with others (Tenenbaum, et al., 2020; Zhang & Bayley, 2019). Students tend to comprehend content more deeply when they are provided opportunities to articulate and clarify their interpretations rather than simply receive information.

Looking back to the initial reasoning underpinning EMI in higher education, if students are not given opportunities to improve their linguistic abilities while simultaneously engaging more deeply with class content, then their linguistic development can remain stagnant and their potential to become part of larger international academic communities diminishes. Put simply, if EMI aims to advance both content learning and English proficiency, then frequent, structured interaction becomes a necessity rather than optional component of the course.

Peer Learning versus Collaborative Learning in EMI

The differences between collaborative learning and peer learning are often blurred and conflated, making it difficult to clearly define and make distinctions between the two. For this paper, the most relevant distinction is that peer learning refers to short, structured exchanges in which students learn “from and with each other” (Boud, 2001, p. 4) without requiring extended group coordination or shared production tasks. Although collaborative learning is widely cited in EMI research, some common forms include sustained group projects, co-authored assignments and long-term group assessment (Storch, 2013). It further tends to assume stable group roles and significant time commitments. These designs are often misaligned with the structural realities of EMI lecture courses, which typically involve quick pacing, large enrollments, and dense content.

In EMI environments where interaction must be frequent, low-burden, and easy to integrate into existing lecture formats, peer learning offers a more scalable and pedagogically compatible alternative. Rather than redesigning courses around group work, peer learning uses the moments within lectures where meaning is processed, allowing students to actively engage with the content in short bursts without disrupting the overall structure of the class.

Since peer learning focuses on short, repeatable, and linguistically scaffolded exchanges rather than long-term interdependence, it aligns more closely with the constraints of EMI settings. Research on peer learning highlights how structured peer interaction supports learning processes in various contexts (Noroozi & De Wever, 2023). Short peer interactions can promote reciprocal reasoning, negotiation of meaning, and shared knowledge building, which are essential for deeper content understanding and language development (Zhang & Bayley, 2019). While collaborative learning approaches remain valuable in many educational settings, peer learning provides a realistic and sustainable model for increasing interaction in EMI lectures while preserving content goals and meeting institutional expectations.

Embedding Peer Learning in EMI Lectures

Interaction checkpoints

Scheduled short pauses throughout the lecture give students opportunities to process, clarify, or verify with a partner or small group. These pauses can be as frequent as the instructor decides, but when pauses are less frequent and the content load is heavier, instructors must provide clearer guidance on what students should focus on, as larger chunks of content place greater cognitive demands on the students. The key to implementing checkpoints effectively is ensuring that each pause includes a structured prompt such as a guiding question, a key concept to review, or a comparison task, so students know exactly how to use the time. Without structure, the interaction may become unfocused or unevenly distributed among students.

Core peer learning strategies

Three tried-and-true peer learning strategies that are effective and easily implemented in EMI lectures are Think-Pair-Share (TPS), mini-summaries, and clarification swaps. Each strategy allows students to critically engage with the content while using English in a lower stress, small group environment, helping to build the confidence needed for whole-class participation. These strategies also promote negotiation of meaning which deepens comprehension and supports both cognitive

and linguistic development. As Chi and Wylie (2014) conclude, as students' learning environments become more active and interactive, they tend to learn more.

In TPS, the instructor poses a question or a problem and allows students time to think individually before discussing their ideas with a partner (Lyman, 1981). During the pair phase, students exchange interpretations, challenge each other's reasoning, and negotiate meaning until they have a clearer and more refined understanding. Finally, selected pairs can share their ideas with the class.

For a richer exchange, the instructor may have students rotate partners and repeat the pair phase to gain different perspectives. TPS activities can be strictly timed to fit within EMI pacing constraints and can be scaffolded with hints, sentence stems, or key vocabulary when tasks are linguistically challenging. Benefits of TPS include giving students processing time before speaking, opportunities to rehearse academic phrases, and repeated exposure to English output. Together, these elements help increase confidence, reduce anxiety, and support both content comprehension and fluency.

Mini summaries are another easily implemented peer learning activity for EMI lectures. At natural transition points, pairs or small groups produce one to three sentence summaries or lists of the key ideas covered. This requires students to identify essential concepts, evaluate their relative importance, and articulate them clearly to peers. Summaries may be shared verbally or posted on the learning management system (LMS). Posting summaries provides instructors with a diagnostic look at student understanding and allows students to compare interpretations across the class. This activity can be scaffolded through academic sentence stems (e.g., "The main argument here is..."; "This concept is significant because..."). For students, the key benefit is deeper understanding through synthesis, and for instructors, summaries provide real-time insight into which concepts require review or clarification.

A final easily implemented activity is a clarification swap, where students are given short opportunities to clarify difficult content with peers. During EMI lectures, students often encounter unfamiliar concepts, specialized terminology, or quick shifts in ideas, which make systematic clarification opportunities invaluable. At designated points, the instructor pauses and instructs students to check with classmates about any parts of the lecture they found difficult to understand. To support this activity, the instructor can list topics on the board or screen. Providing functional expressions such as "Can you clarify...?", "How did you interpret...?", or "My understanding is ..., but I'm not sure about ..." helps students lower linguistic barriers and increases the productivity of the exchange. Clarification swaps help students catch misunderstandings early and reinforce comprehension through peer explanation.

Limitations

While this article has argued for implementing short peer exchanges to increase interaction as a way to address the gap between EMI policy and practice, there are some limitations to consider. First, this article draws on theory and classroom experience rather than empirical classroom observations. As a result, the arguments and recommendations offered here should be interpreted as theoretically grounded and practitioner-informed rather than empirically validated. Future classroom-based studies would strengthen the evidence base for the peer learning approach outlined in this paper. Typically, more interaction and active participation leads to students feeling a sense

of ownership over their education which can increase engagement and confidence (Mercer, 2019), but this outcome is not guaranteed and can vary across classes and proficiency levels.

From an implementation perspective, some instructors may feel that they are giving up their control of the class while students participate in peer exchanges. This concern can be exacerbated when students use their first language (L1) during the interaction or when they observe uneven participation among students. These can be significant hurdles to overcome but instructors who are sensitive to these issues may adapt the exchanges to include individual reflective writing submissions after each class, or by briefly joining pairs or groups during exchanges to monitor understanding and engagement.

Additionally, peer learning exchanges may not fully address all sources of limited interaction in EMI settings, such as institutional exam pressures, curriculum pacing requirements, or students' beliefs about appropriate classroom behavior. These broader constraints may require institutional changes beyond classroom practices. Despite these limitations, short peer exchanges remain a practical and adaptable option for EMI instructors seeking to increase interaction without compromising content instruction goals.

Conclusion

While the adoption and spread of EMI in higher education has succeeded in terms of policy reach, the pedagogical implementation is often lacking. The disconnect tends to be that the implementation does not match the reasoning. Students are expected to gain a deep understanding of the class content through English, but they are not given practical and structured opportunities to use English to engage with that content meaningfully. Without intentional interactional design, EMI risks becoming a passive, receptive mode of learning that does not support content comprehension or language development.

Peer learning offers a practical resolution to this problem. It does not replace lectures, reduce content coverage, or include broad curricular redesign. Instead, it reframes interaction itself by embedding short exchanges that allow students to think together, clarify their ideas, negotiate meaning, and reflect on their understanding of the class content. These exchanges can convert passive lecture reception into dialogic knowledge processing. When peer learning becomes routine in EMI classrooms it has the potential to shift the way students learn in meaningful ways. By adding short peer exchanges, the focus of lectures can transform from a one-way instructor-centered mode to a more inclusive classroom that distributes the cognitive load and allows students to become more active participants in the learning process while they have more practice speaking and using English during classes.

Short peer learning exchanges have the potential to change EMI lectures from domains where students silently receive information to active environments where students can communicate reasoning. They can also shift the responsibility of content teaching from the instructor to the class as a whole and move students from feeling pressured to be accurate to a position where they can potentially negotiate meaning with their peers.

The outcome is not only improved language use, but deeper content learning, greater participation equity, and a more inclusive model of engagement. Peer learning thus represents a pedagogically efficient and class-time-compatible strategy for changing EMI lectures into more interactive learning spaces. EMI courses do not need to choose between content coverage and interactive

learning as structured short peer learning exchanges make both achievable and aligned with the original goals of EMI policy.

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